

EXPERIMENTS TOWARDS THE SYNTHESIS OF ANALGESICS.

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The syntheses of 1-(2'-furyl)-3:4-dihydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline, 1-(7'-methoxy 2'-coumaronyl)-3:4-dihydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline, and 1-(*α*'-phenanthryl)-3:4-dihydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline and their *N*-methyltetrahydro derivatives are reported.

Morphine is recognised as one of the best known natural analgesics. "Euphoria" leads to repeated administration of the drug, which in turn causes "addiction". Innumerable attempts have been made to prepare simple, and easily accessible synthetic substances, having the analgesic activity of morphine, but devoid of its undesirable effects (Small, Mosettig, Eddy and others, *U.S. Public Health Reports, suppl.*, 1938, 138). In morphine there are furan, coumarone, dibenzofuran, isoquinoline skeletons present. Any one of these may prove to be the basic structure for its analgesic properties.

Considering morphine as an amino-alcohol Mosettig and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 3448; 1935, **57**, 2189; 1936, **58**, 1570, 1311) have synthesised a large number of simpler amino-alcohols derived from phenanthrene, dibenzofuran and carbazole derivatives, which were found by Eddy and co-workers (*J. Phar. Expt. Therap.*, 1933, **48**, 175; 1935, **55**, 419) to possess some interesting physiological properties. Mosettig and co-workers (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, **3**, 317; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2962; 1940, **62**, 1110) have also synthesised other substances *e.g.* benzoquinolines, naphthaquinolines, dibenzoisoquinolines and naphthaisoquinolines. The former two types of compounds were found to be either weak or entirely ineffective as analgesics (Eddy, *J. Phar. Expt. Therap.*, 1936, **58**, 159). The above authors prepared 1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphtha-(1:2h)-isoquinoline and 1:2:3:4-tetrahydrodibenzo-(f:h)-isoquinoline by cyclising the formaldehyde condensation products of 2-(2-aminoethyl)-phenanthrene and 9-(2-aminoethyl)-phenanthrene respectively by Decker and Becker method, the Bischler-Napieralski reaction not succeeding (1938, *loc. cit.*)

The present investigations were undertaken to synthesise isoquinoline derivatives possessing the structural groups such as furan, coumarone, phenanthrene, etc., from the simpler and easily accessible homopiperonylamine as the starting material according to the following scheme :

Homopiperonylamine, prepared according to Buck and Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **126**, 1693) has been condensed with (i) ethyl α -furoate

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(Schwanert, *Annalen*, 1860, 116, 267); (ii) methyl 7-methoxycoumarone-2-carboxylate; (iii) 9-phenanthroyl chloride (Mosettig and Kamp, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 3448); (iv) ethyl β -2-furylpropionate (Windaus and Dalmer, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 2304) and (v) ethyl β -2-(5-phenyl)-furyl propionate (Robinson and Todd, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1743) to give the amides (I), (IV), (VII), (X) and (XI) respectively. Out of these only the amide (IV), (X) and (XI) are well defined crystalline solids.

The cyclisation of the amides (I), (IV) and (VII) to the corresponding 1-(2'-furyl)-3:4-dihydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (V), 1-(7'-methoxy-2'-coumaronyl)-3:4-dihydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (V), and 1-(9'-phenanthryl)-3:4-dihydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (VIII) respectively, is effected easily and in good yield by gently refluxing with phosphorus oxychloride in dry toluene solution. Attempts to effect the cyclisation of the amides (X) and (XI) under a variety of conditions resulted only in tarry non-basic products. The reduction of the methiodides of the dihydro bases to the corresponding *N*-methyltetrahydro bases is effected readily by heating on the water-bath with zinc and dilute sulphuric acid. These are oils and are characterised as picrates.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-(2'-Furyl)-3:4-dihydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (II).—A mixture of homopiperonylamine (2 g.) and ethyl furoate (1.53 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 24 hours. An ethereal solution of the reaction product was purified by washing with dilute hydrochloric acid followed by water, drying over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and then removing the solvent. The crude amide, thus obtained, was treated with dry toluene (20 c.c.) and phosphorus oxychloride (10 c.c.). The mixture was gently refluxed for 1 hour (guard tube), cooled and poured with stirring on to crushed ice. The resulting solution after freeing from non-basic impurities by repeated extraction with benzene, was thoroughly cooled, basified with concentrated ammonia, and extracted with ether. The ether extract after drying over anhydrous potassium carbonate and evaporation of the solvent, yielded the dihydro base, which crystallised from dilute alcohol in long, colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 95-96°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 69.39; H, 4.49; N, 5.86. $C_{14}H_{11}O_3N$ requires C, 69.72; H, 4.57; N, 5.81 per cent).

The *picrate* crystallised from dilute alcohol in long, shining yellow needles, m.p. 206° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.93. $C_{20}H_{14}O_6N_4$ requires N, 11.91 per cent).

The methiodide crystallised from chloroform-petrol in short, bright yellow needles, m.p. 238° (decomp.). (Found: I, 34·21. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2NI$ requires I, 33·19 per cent).

1-(2'-Furyl)-N-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (III).—A mixture of the methiodide of the dihydro base (0·5 g.), dilute sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) and zinc dust (5 g.) was heated on a water-bath till the colour of the solution completely disappeared. The reaction mixture was filtered hot, the residue was washed with hot dilute sulphuric acid and the filtrate after freeing from non-basic impurities by extracting with benzene, was thoroughly cooled, basified with concentrated ammonia and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution after drying and evaporation yielded the tetrahydro base as a viscous oil which was characterised as the picrate crystallising from dilute alcohol in short yellow needles, m.p. 99-100° (decomp.). (Found: C, 51·96; H, 3·74; N, 11·57. $C_{21}H_{18}O_{10}N_4$ requires C, 51·86; H, 3·7; N, 5·3 per cent).

Methyl 7-Methoxycoumarone-2-carboxylate.—7-Methoxycoumarone-2-carboxylic acid (12 g.), prepared according to the method of Reichstein and co-workers (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1935, 18, 819) was esterified by saturating an absolute alcoholic solution with dry hydrochloric acid. The resulting ester was worked up in the usual way and was crystallised from dilute alcohol in long white needles, m.p. 79°, yield 7 g. (Found: C, 63·62; H, 4·94. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64·07; H, 4·85 per cent).

7-Methoxy-2-coumaronylhomopiperonylamide (IV).—A mixture of homopiperonylamine (2 g.) and methyl 7-methoxycoumarone-2-carboxylate (2·5 g.) was heated on a water-bath for 24 hours. After isolation in the usual way, the crude amide was crystallised from toluene-petroleum ether in white clustres of needles, m.p. 86°, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 66·99; H, 5·09; N, 4·19. $C_{19}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 67·25; H, 5·01; N, 4·13 per cent).

1-(7'-Methoxy-2'-coumaronyl)-3:4-dihydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (V).—A mixture of 7-methoxy-2-coumaronylhomopiperonylamide (2 g.), dry toluene (20 c.c.) and phosphorus oxychloride (10 c.c.) was gently refluxed for 1 hour with exclusion of moisture. The reaction mixture after decomposition with crushed ice, was freed from non-basic impurities by extraction with benzene, then thoroughly cooled, basified and the liberated dihydro base extracted with ether. From the dried ethereal solution (potassium carbonate) the dihydro base, obtained as residue, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in long colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 140-42°, yield 1·5 g. (Found: C, 71·31; H, 4·61; N, 4·44. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4N$ requires C, 71·03; H, 4·67; N, 4·36 per cent).

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The *picrate* crystallised from dilute alcohol in short yellow needles, m.p. 220° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10'13. $C_{25}H_{18}O_{11}N_4$ requires N, 10'18 per cent).

The *methiodide* crystallised from chloroform-benzene-petrol in orange yellow, long, rectangular plates, m.p. $190-91^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found: I, 27'78. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4NI$ requires I, 27'43 per cent).

1-(7'-Methoxy-2'-coumaronyl)-N-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (VI).—The methiodide of the dihydro base (1 g.) was reduced with dilute sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) and zinc dust (5 g.) as before. The product after isolation, as described before in an analogous case, was an oil which was converted into the *picrate*. The *picrate* crystallised from dilute alcohol in dull yellow plates, m.p. $185-87^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found: C, 55'42; H, 3'92; N, 10'02. $C_{22}H_{26}O_{11}N_4$ requires C, 55'12; H, 3'89; N, 9'9 per cent).

1-(9'-Phenanthryl)-3:4-dihydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (VIII).—Homopiperonylamine (2 g.) and 9-phenanthroyl chloride (3 g.) were condensed in presence of concentrated potassium hydroxide solution. The resulting amide was extracted with ether, repeatedly washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, water, then dried and the solvent removed by distillation. The crude amide, dry toluene (20 c.c.) and phosphorus oxychloride (10 c.c.) were gently refluxed for 1 hour with the exclusion of moisture. The product was isolated as before. The oily dihydro base gave a *picrate*.

The *picrate* crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining yellow prisms, m.p. $145-47^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found: C, 61'39; H, 3'46; N, 10'3. $C_{30}H_{20}O_9N_4$ requires C, 62'17; H, 3'45; N, 9'7 per cent).

1-(9'-Phenanthryl)-N-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-6:7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (IX).—The methiodide of the dihydro base (0'5 g.) was reduced with dilute sulphuric acid (30 c.c.) and zinc dust (5 g.) as described before. The tetrahydro base, liberated with ammonia, was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract dried (anhydrous potassium carbonate) and the solvent removed by distillation. The oily base was converted into a *picrate*.

The *picrate* crystallised from dilute alcohol in dull yellow needles, m.p. $105-8^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found: C, 62'67; H, 4'07; N, 9'52. $C_{31}H_{24}O_9N_4$ requires C, 62'41; H, 4'02; N, 9'40 per cent).

β -2-Furylpropionylhomopiperonylamide (X).—A mixture of homopiperonylamine (2 g.), ethyl β -2-furylpropionate (2'06 g.) was heated on a water-bath for 24 hours. The resulting amide was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract, after washing with dilute hydrochloric acid and water, was dried and the solvent removed. The amide crystallised from dilute

alcohol in short shining needles, m.p. 92° , yield 3 g. (Found: C, 67.33; H, 5.91; N, 3.89. $C_{16}H_{17}O_4N$ requires C, 66.80; H, 5.92; N, 4.88 per cent).

β -2-(5-Phenyl)-furylpropionylhomopiperonylamide (XI).—Homopiperonylamine (2 g.), β -2-(5-phenyl)-furyl propionate (2.5 g.) were condensed by heating on the water-bath for 24 hours. The resulting amide was purified and separated as in the above experiment. The amide crystallised from dilute alcohol in short shining plates, m.p. $104-5^{\circ}$, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 73.1; H, 5.92; N, 4.05. $C_{22}H_{21}O_4N$ requires C, 74.7; H, 5.99; N, 3.87 per cent).

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